

Comparison of the Relational Dimension with Weaving Models

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This document is supplementary material accompanying the paper titled "Microservice-based model-driven architecture for implementing modeling and model-transformation as a service". This supplementary document contrasts the Relational Dimension of MDOA with the Weaving Model approach as implemented in the Eclipse AMW plugin. While both mechanisms capture relationships between model elements, the Relational Dimension specializes in unidirectional abstraction-level integration and is embedded within the modeling infrastructure, avoiding separate weaving artifacts. The comparison covers purpose, scope, artifact management, multiplicity, semantics, and tool support. A tabular summary outlines the trade-offs between the two approaches.

Comparison of the Relational Dimension with Weaving Models

The concept of Relational Dimension introduced in the proposed Model-Driven Onion Architecture (MDOA) bears certain similarities to the Weaving Model [1] approach described in Weaving Models with the Eclipse AMW plugin, yet differs in scope, purpose, and implementation. Both approaches aim to capture relationships between model elements, but their underlying design principles and operational contexts diverge.

Purpose and Scope.

The Weaving Model approach captures semantic relationships between elements of two or more models, supporting a variety of scenarios such as transformation specification, traceability, and model alignment. It is a generic mechanism, with link semantics defined by the application context. In contrast, the Relational Dimension is a specialized mechanism designed to establish unidirectional links from domain objects in a lower-level model (e.g., PSM or PIM) to domain concepts at a higher level of abstraction (e.g., PIM or CIM). This specialization supports abstraction-level integration while preserving the independence of higher-level models from lower-level implementation concerns.

Table 1: Purpose and Scope

Aspect	Relational Dimension (RD)	Weaving Model (WM)
Purpose	Creates a unidirectional link from a domain object (lower-level model) to a domain concept (higher-level abstraction).	Captures relationships between elements of (two or more) models for different scenarios (traceability, transformation specification, alignment, etc.).
Additional Model?	Does not require generating a separate weaving model — links are part of the existing modeling infrastructure.	Requires creating a weaving model (Mw) that conforms to a weaving metamodel, stored as a separate artifact.
Scope	Specifically targets abstraction-level connections (e.g., PSM→PIM, PIM→CIM) while preserving independence between levels.	General-purpose, can represent semantic relationships of any kind between model elements across arbitrary models.

Artifact Management.

Weaving Models are realized as separate artifacts conforming to a weaving metamodel. Each weaving model contains references to elements in the related models, requiring identification and resolution mechanisms for each endpoint. Conversely, the Relational Dimension is embedded directly within the modeling infrastructure, eliminating the need to generate or manage an additional weaving model. Links are stored as properties of the participating model elements, enabling direct access without an intermediary artifact.

Link Semantics and Multiplicity.

Both approaches support multiple link types and varying arities. In the Weaving Model approach, link types (e.g., equality, concatenation, modified) are defined in the weaving metamodel and instantiated in the weaving model. In the Relational Dimension, the semantics are expressed through two properties: Relation Name and Relation Target. This allows:

1. Multiple Relational Dimensions from the same domain object to the same domain concept with different relation names.
2. Relational Dimensions from one domain object to multiple domain concepts.
3. Multiple domain objects to share the same Relational Dimension to a single domain concept.

Table 2: Link Semantics and Multiplicity

Aspect	Relational Dimension	Weaving Model
Multiplicity	One domain object can: 1. Have multiple RD links to the same concept with different relation names. 2. Link to multiple different domain concepts. 3. Share a concept link with many other domain objects.	Supports different link types (equality, concatenation, added, modified, generated, replaced, etc.). Links may be unary, binary, ternary, etc., and can point to elements in more than two models.
Interpretation	Meaning defined by Relation Name and Relation Target (the concept).	Semantics depend entirely on link type and the application scenario (merge, traceability, alignment, etc.).
Location of Links	Links are embedded in the model data itself, avoiding a separate Mw artifact.	Links stored in Mw, which holds references (not copies) to elements in other models.
Access	Direct, since no extra model needs to be resolved.	Requires resolving references through Mw to get to target elements.
Uniqueness Mechanism	Identified by domain object + relation name + target concept.	Requires an identification mechanism in the weaving metamodel for each endpoint reference.

Creation and Maintenance.

Weaving Models can be created manually using graphical editors, generated automatically through matching heuristics, or produced as a byproduct of transformation execution (e.g., for traceability). The Relational Dimension, by contrast, is established directly during model creation or refinement, and can also be added automatically during model-to-model transformations. Because it is stored alongside model data, maintenance is integrated into existing modeling workflows without requiring specialized weaving tooling.

Table 3: Creation and Maintenance

Aspect	Relational Dimension	Weaving Model
Manual Creation	Added directly when defining or refining domain objects in the lower-level model.	Can be created manually using graphical weaving editors.
Automatic Creation	Could be added during transformation (e.g., when generating lower-level models from higher ones).	Often generated by matching heuristics or as a byproduct of transformation execution (e.g., traceability weaving model).
Tooling Requirements	No special weaving editor — is integrated into MDDPlatform modeling and transformation tools.	Requires tooling that understands weaving metamodels and can create/edit Mw.

Reusability and Transformation Integration.

Both approaches support reuse, but with differing emphases. Weaving Models achieve reusability by decoupling link specifications from transformation languages, allowing independent management and later translation into executable transformations. The Relational Dimension achieves reusability by maintaining stable, runtime-accessible links across abstraction levels. These links guide transformations that merge higher-level concept information into lower-level models while avoiding propagation of changes from lower to higher levels, thus reducing model overlap and supporting round-trip engineering control.

Aspect	Relational Dimension	Weaving Model
Reusability	Facilitates model refinement and merging without breaking abstraction boundaries; supports runtime linking.	Promotes reusability by decoupling relationships from transformation languages, enabling independent link management.
Transformation Use	Links can guide model-to-model transformations to merge higher-level concept details into lower-level objects.	Links can act as specifications for transformations, to be later translated into executable transformation languages.
Round-trip Engineering	Explicitly designed to prevent propagation of changes from lower-level to higher-level models.	Can support bidirectional relationships, but higher-level model stability depends on transformation setup.

Summary of Differences.

While the Weaving Model is a general-purpose relationship-capturing mechanism applicable across diverse modeling scenarios, the Relational Dimension can be regarded as a specialized, integrated subset of its capabilities. It is optimized for abstraction-level linking in multi-level architectures, eliminates the overhead of managing a separate weaving artifact, and directly reflects domain semantics through relation names and targets. This makes it particularly well-suited for the MDOA context, where maintaining independence between abstraction levels and minimizing model management complexity are primary objectives.

References

- [1] M. Didonet, M. Fabro, J. Bézivin, and P. Valduriez, “Weaving Models with the Eclipse AMW plugin,” Jul. 2008.